

THE ROLE OF COMMUNICATION SERVICES IN THE NATIONAL AND
WORLD ECONOMY

Allayorov Kh.I.

independent researcher of SamIES

Abstract. In this article, the opportunities of communication services in our country today and its place in the world market, the importance of communication services in the national and world economy, the stages of development of national communication services are highlighted by the author.

Key words: communication services, world economy, communication models, service delivery areas.

The socio-economic development of the service sector, according to its content, is aimed at increasing the quality of life and quality of life, creating optimal conditions for the development of human capital associated with the formation of modern industries, and the distribution of a relatively high level of division of labor. covers various directions of economic activity.

In the conditions of the transformation of the economy, the service sector is economically more efficient than industrial production, because the implementation of initial activities in the service sector requires less funds, and the turnover rate of capital is much higher.

Currently, in the conditions of the transformation of the economy, the continuous and stable development of service enterprises and the improvement of the socio-economic mechanism of increasing efficiency in ensuring the intensity of service is considered a particularly urgent issue, and it means that the processes of transformation of communication services should be accelerated.

Communication is essential for economic development. It allows businesses to operate efficiently, connect with customers, and innovate. It also allows governments to provide essential services and coordinate economic policies.

Body: There are many different ways in which communication contributes to economic development. Some examples include:

- **Improving business efficiency:** Communication technologies allow businesses to reduce costs and improve productivity. For example, businesses can use email and video conferencing to communicate with customers and suppliers around the world.

- **Connecting businesses with customers:** Communication technologies allow businesses to reach a wider audience and build relationships with customers. For example, businesses can use social media to connect with customers and promote their products and services.

- **Promoting innovation:** Communication technologies allow businesses to share information and collaborate on new ideas. For example, businesses can use online platforms to share research and development findings with other businesses and researchers.

Communication is the economy's engine for change and its gateway to new resources and opportunities. It connects key players in the economy, promotes their dialogue and informs their policies.

It empowers marginalised communities and gives them a voice to influence the decisions that affect their enterprises and their livelihoods.

Our communication interventions in innovation, sustainable tourism and economic development expand from managing advocacy campaigns to promoting positive change and raising awareness of different socio-economic issues.

We see various forms of communications as complementary but necessary tactics to expedite the progress of economic development and achieve sustainable development goals. We leverage diverse communication tactics to change

behaviour, produce and disseminate information, engage stakeholders, and facilitate dialogue.

Leaders International capitalises on an extensive local and global network of experts and partners to inspire through human-interest stories and educate through insightful assessment and research. In doing so, we pay acute attention to media preferences of different audiences, the local context and the specific needs of vulnerable communities.

Delivering measurable impact across different sectors is the core of our communication interventions, whether through empowering women, fostering entrepreneurial cultures, marketing destinations or promoting public-private partnerships.

Communication for economic development is as well our force multiplier to deliver results that guarantee social inclusion and instigate change.

Our experience in managing and delivering communication activities includes but is not limited to the following:

- Project visibility and branding;
- Awareness and behavioural change;
- Advocacy and policy dialogue;
- Public diplomacy and outreach;
- Destination marketing and travel PR;
- Trade promotion;
- Marketing communications support for beneficiaries (MSMEs and startups).

Particular attention is paid to the development and implementation of organizational and economic measures to reduce the impact of imbalances in the field of communications on their efficiency. We found it necessary to include the following among such measures:

-First, to ensure the development of science-based norms and standards of service quality, taking into account the number of interruptions in the design of

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equipment and communication networks and the correct distribution of their number of employees in the workplace;

-secondly, the creation of optimal schedules of shifts and vacations of employees engaged in the provision of communication services, the implementation of operating modes of communication organizations, flexible tariff policy, etc;

-Thirdly, unlike industrial enterprises, the object of labor undergoes material changes (mechanical, economy, chemical, etc.), enters the sphere of circulation, becomes a commodity and only then is consumed.

The telecommunication industry contributes vastly to how businesses operate, enabling them to improve services, reach new markets, and keep in touch with customers. It has also allowed e-commerce and remote work to flourish amidst challenges like inadequate infrastructure, cybersecurity, and the digital divide.

That is why governments must employ initiatives to address these setbacks and ensure that the industry contributes further to enabling economic growth.

In addition, and probably essential, is the need for mid-market companies to partner with reliable system integrators, such as Unisol International, to leverage the latest technology for their telecommunications systems.

Unisol International prides itself on being an industry leader dedicated to offering product distribution and turnkey deployments of IP Networking solutions, especially in electronic security, telecommunications, and professional audio/video. Our wide range of products and services can help businesses stay competitive, allowing them to invest in the most up-to-date technologies for their telecommunications needs.

With our expertise and experience, you can count on us for access to cutting-edge technology and support throughout your project lifecycle. Please contact us for more information about our products and services.

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